

ON THE PREPARATION OF SULPHANILAMIDE DERIVATIVES.
PART III. SULPHATHIAZOLES

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A method has been described by which various sulphathiazoles may be prepared by the action of yellow ammonium sulphide on an alkali salt of sulphanilycyanamide and subsequent condensation of the resulting sulphanilylthiourea with chloroaldehydes and ketones.

Sulphathiazole (2-*p*-aminobenzenesulphonamidothiazole) (I) is a valuable antibacterial agent, particularly against pneumococcus (Mckee *et al.*, *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.*, 1939, 42, 410). It is generally prepared by the action of 2-aminothiazole on *p*-acetaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride and subsequent hydrolysis (Fosbinder and Walter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2032; Svensk, *Kem. Tid.* 1942, 52, 64) according to the following equations :—

By another process (Indian Patent No. 26850) the same compound has been obtained from *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide and 2-bromothiazole. By yet another process (I.P. 28108) this compound is obtained from *p*-acetaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride and sodium derivative of 2-aminothiazole and subsequent hydrolysis.

In Part II (Das-gupta and Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 327) it has been shown that the cyanamide grouping of sulphanilycyanamide reacts with ammonia to give rise to sulphaguanidine.

Cyanamide is known (Baumann, *Ber.*, 1875, 8, 26) to react with sulphuretted hydrogen to give rise to thiourea

As thiourea again readily reacts with α -haloid keto compounds (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 3127) to give rise to aminothiazoles according to the equation

it has been considered to be of interest to study the above reactions with sulphanilylcynamide, prepared according to the method previously described by us in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 324) by reacting *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide with ethyl sulphocyanide, in the expectation of working out a process for the manufacture of sulphathiazole according to the following scheme :

This expectation has been fully realised and the details of the experimental procedure are embodied in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Aminobenzenesulphonylthiourea.—Sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzenesulphonylcyanamide (20 g.) was added to a saturated solution of yellow ammonium sulphide (150 c.c.) and the solution left as such for 40 hours. The solution was then evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the residue again treated with water, and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with dilute acid gave a solid turning yellow mercuric oxide black. *p*-Aminobenzenesulphonylthiourea crystallised from water in needles, m.p. 169-70°. (Found: N, 18.2; S, 27.9. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ requires N, 18.18; S, 27.7 per cent).

p-Acetaminobenzenesulphonylthiourea.—The sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzenesulphonylcyanamide, isolated by reacting the sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzenesulphonylcyanamide (27 g.) with ethyl sulphocyanide, was dissolved in about 200 c.c. water. Saturated yellow ammonium sulphide solution (80 c.c.) was added to it in cold and the solution kept at the room temperature for 40 hours. It was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated off on a water-bath. The residue was boiled with water and filtered to remove any undesirable by-product. The filtrate on acidification afforded *p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphonylthiourea, m.p. 195°. (Found: N, 15.18; S, 23.4. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ requires N, 15.38; S, 23.48 per cent).

2-(*p*-Aminobenzene sulphonamido)-thiazole.—Dichloroethyl ether (12.0 g.) was suspended in water in a conical flask and mixed with calcium carbonate (4 g.). The calcium carbonate went into solution and the solution became neutral to congo-red, *p*-Aminobenzenesulphonylthiourea in the form of its sodium salt (20 g.) was added to the above solution which was refluxed for 1 hour. The hot solution was decanted into a beaker and allowed to cool. Reddish brown crystals were obtained which were first crystallised from water and then from dilute alcohol. This melted at 202° and gave all characteristics of 2-(*p*-aminobenzenesulphonamido)thiazole. (Found: N, 16.8. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ requires N, 16.47 per cent).

2-(*p*-Acetaminobenzenesulphonamido)-thiazole.—Dichloroethyl ether (15 g.) was treated with sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzenesulphonylthiourea (30 g.) in the way as illustrated in the above example and the mixture refluxed on a wire gauge for 2 hours. The reaction mixture on cooling gave a reddish brown mass which crystallised from dilute

alcohol, m.p. 256°. (Found : N, 14.25. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3N_3S_2$ requires N, 14.14 per cent). On hydrolysing with caustic soda solution (10%) it afforded 2-(*p*-aminobenzene-sulphonamido)-thiazole, m.p. 202°.

2-(*p*-*Ar* inobenzene-sulphonamido)-4-methylthiazole.—The sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene-sulphonylthiourea was taken in absolute alcohol and then refluxed with molecular proportion of chloroacetone for about 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was diluted with water when crystals separated out. This on recrystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 237° without sintering when admixed with an authentic sample of 2-(*p*-aminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4-methylthiazole. (Found : N, 15.72. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_3S_2$: N, 15.6 per cent.)

2-(*p*-Aminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4-phenylthiazole.—2-(*p*-Aminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4-phenylthiazole, m.p. 190°, was similarly obtained by reacting the sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene-sulphonylthiourea with ω -bromoacetophenone in a way as illustrated above. (Found : N, 12.9. $C_{15}H_{13}O_2N_3S_2$ requires N, 12.7 per cent.)

2-(*p*-Aminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4 : 5-tetrahydrobenzothiazole.—The sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene-sulphonylthiourea was similarly reacted in molecular proportion with 2-chlorocyclohexanone in alcoholic suspension. The reaction mixture on subsequent treatment afforded 2-(*p*-aminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4 : 5-tetrahydrobenzothiazole, m.p. 154° already described by Basu and Das-gupta (*J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1941, 18, 167). (Found : N, 12.70 ; H_2O , 5.4. $C_{13}H_{15}O_2N_3S_2$, H_2O requires N, 12.84 ; H_2O , 5.5 per cent.)

2-(*p*-Acetaminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4-methylthiazole.—Sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzene-sulphonylthiourea, as prepared before, was refluxed with molecular proportion of chloroacetone in absolute alcohol for about 20 minutes. The reaction mixture was cooled and diluted with water when a solid separated out. This melted at 259° and on hydrolysis with alkali in the customary way afforded 2-(*p*-aminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4-methylthiazole. (Found : N, 13.65. $C_{12}H_{13}O_3N_3S_2$ requires N, 13.5 per cent.)

2-(*p*-Acetaminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4-phenylthiazole.—Sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylthiourea was treated as above with ω -bromoacetophenone. The acetyl derivative first isolated melted at 235° and this on hydrolysis in the usual way afforded 2-(*p*-aminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4-phenylthiazole. (Found : N, 11.5. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N_3S_2$ requires N, 11.3 per cent.)

2-(*p*-Acetaminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4 : 5-tetrahydrobenzothiazole.—2-Chlorocyclohexanone and sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzene-sulphonylthiourea when reacted as above gave a thiazole derivative, m.p. 180°, which on hydrolysis as usual gave 2-(*p*-aminobenzene-sulphonamido)-4 : 5-tetrahydrobenzothiazole. (Found : N, 11.5 ; H_2O , 5.0. $C_{13}H_{17}O_3N_3S_2$, H_2O requires N, 11.4 ; H_2O , 4.9 per cent.)

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